

Summary: A landscape study on open access (OA) and monographs

Policies, funding and publishing in eight European countries

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Title: Summary: A landscape study on open access (OA) and monographs

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Full report authored by: Eelco Ferwerda, Frances Pinter and Niels Stern

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Contents

About this summary	2
About the project	2
The context for OA monographs	3
Direction of travel	4
Characteristics of OA monograph policies	5
Country studies	6
Open access policy environment	6
Open access practices	6
Monograph publishing	7
Austria	8
Germany	9
The Netherlands	9
France	10
United Kingdom	10
Denmark	11
Finland	11
Norway	11
New approaches to making monographs OA	13
Information gaps and future research direction	14
Recommendations to OA stakeholders	15

About this summary

Knowledge Exchange¹, a multi-national collaboration to support the development of digital infrastructure to enable open scholarship, commissioned a landscape study to analyse existing information about how OA monographs operate in the six KE countries, as well as Norway and Austria.

The full report, authored by Eelco Ferwerda, Frances Pinter and Niels Stern, is available at knowledge-exchange.info/event/open-access-monographs.

This summary provides an overview of the key areas, but is by no means a substitute for the rich information contained in the full report.

About the project

The brief for this project contained two main objectives:

- ▶ Analyse existing information about OA monographs in relation to OA policies, funding streams and business models
- ▶ Establish information gaps or areas where Knowledge Exchange could contribute to the development of OA monographs

The resulting study drew on a literature review, a series of web-based questionnaires and qualitative interviews to understand the ecology of OA monographs in different countries.

The main report is divided into four sections:

- ▶ Part 1 (chapters 1-4) scope, methods and overview of general themes; recommendations to KE
- ▶ Part 2 (chapters 5-6) individual country studies
- ▶ Part 3 (chapters 7-8) notable initiatives, information gaps and recommendations to stakeholders
- ▶ Part 4 (chapters 9-16) appendices, including literature review, further analysis of book processing charges (BPCs), techniques for assessing impact of OA monographs and research materials

Footnotes

- 1 knowledge-exchange.info
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The context for OA monographs

Findings in the key areas of OA monograph business models, policies and funding streams were strongly influenced by:

- ▶ The circumstances and culture in each of the countries
- ▶ The wider scholarly communications environment as it relates to open access and monographs

Many kinds of developments and activities contribute to the specific set of circumstances observed in each country. Changes can be (but aren't always) influenced

by multinational developments, such as EU policies or funding streams, or international publishing standards, or changing disciplinary norms. They can also be influenced by highly localised – national or even regional – contexts: a country's monograph publishing infrastructure, local scholarly culture, wage patterns or historic patterns of engagement with open access.

In most countries, there is a narrative around the 'decline' of the monograph, typically represented by falling sales. OA can often be positioned as a solution to this problem.

Figure 1

Direction of travel

Although robust and comparable data are hard to gather, both open access monographs and the policies and models that support them seem to be growing.

245 OA policies worldwide including books or sections of books	85 of these are mandates
Est. 10,000 OA monograph titles available globally in English	At least 200 publishers offering OA options for monograph authors

Even within countries there can be considerable variation: institutions, private funders and government agencies support OA monographs in different ways. In general, policies offer recommendations rather than mandates, but monographs are increasingly part of broader conversations about open access. And mandates do exist: for example, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) in the Netherlands and the Wellcome Trust in the UK all mandate OA for monographs, as does the European Research Council.

Where policies, recommendations or mandates exist they tend to be less restrictive than those for journal publishing; more flexible about licence type and embargo periods, and less rigorously enforced or even monitored. Most national policies focus on journal articles and, where they mention monographs, do so as an addendum or area of emerging practice; some explicitly exclude them².

Publisher practices are similarly diverse. Influenced by historic publishing business models, local approaches to quality assurance, changing markets for their scholarly output and different types of demand, the offer is not the same across or even within countries: indeed, individual publishers may offer several different routes to

open access³. Without robust evidence about the impact of OA publishing on sales, publishers must rely on their own judgement and knowledge to decide an appropriate funding structure. But certain parts of the publishing industry have less distance to travel than others in order to reach a viable OA publishing process and business model: institutions, publishers or countries with established 'pay to publish' mechanisms and a developed transition to digital will find the move easier, for example⁴.

Institutional engagement in moves towards open access monographs tend to be positive across all countries in the study, but again the specific extent and characteristics of this engagement is dictated by local circumstances⁵. Some institutions are further ahead than others, but collaboration is common in all countries in the study: research organisations work together to identify options and opportunities.

In every country, a particular development, organisation or even individual has been key to driving forward the open access monograph agenda. Generally speaking, the main barrier to further progress is not securing funding. Rather, it is finding ways to re-channel existing funding streams to support open access models; a lack of policies supporting OA books and low awareness of the benefits of OA among authors.

Footnotes

- ² For more on monograph inclusion in OA policies, see [section 3.3](#) of the full report.
- ³ For more on publisher engagement with OA monographs and business models offered, see [section 3.4](#) and [3.5](#) of the full report.
- ⁴ For more on industry or supply chain aspects which help or hinder transition to OA, see [section 3.6](#) of the full report.
- ⁵ For more on institutional engagement with OA monographs, see [section 3.6.7](#) of the full report.

Characteristics of OA monograph policies⁶

Funder requirements for OA monographs consider many dimensions of the publishing process. Other stakeholders – publishers in particular – must be aware that their OA monograph practices need to accommodate diversity on every dimension.

Dimension	Detail
Scope of policy	Policies may include monographs, edited collections, book chapters or any combination of these: they may also be different for different kinds of book.
Maximum embargo period	The maximum embargo period for open access may range from nothing (if publication is funded) to several months or even years.
Funding available	Funding that is available to underpin the costs of open access monograph publishing may be time-limited, and unavailable once the original research grant is closed. Conversely, some funders will support the costs of open access books even if those books are based on research they did not fund.
Licence (if Gold OA)	Funders may require a specific Creative Commons licence, or may simply state the licence conditions that are acceptable.
Self-archiving of author manuscript	Some funders may require this; policies may differ based on how the original publication was funded.
Repository	Deposit in a repository may be required – the funder may or may not specify the repository to be used.
Deposit timing and process	Policies around deposit may vary depending on whether Gold or Green OA is used. Authors, publishers or both may be responsible for deposit.

Footnotes

⁶ For examples of funder OA policies, see [section 3.3](#), especially Table 4 of the full report.

Country studies

Section 6 of the full report – the longest section – provides rich information on the landscape, activities and direction of travel for open access monographs in each of the eight countries in the study. This summary sketches some high-level similarities and differences across the countries, and provides an overview of each country's direction of travel.

Open access policy environment

Countries have reached different stages in their moves towards open access policies, and existing policy positions affect how key actors perceive monograph options.

Funding models matter. In some countries, such as the Netherlands, Gold is strongly preferred while in others, such as Denmark, the presumption is that open access will be achieved via the Green route. Many countries operate a mixed economy, with the decision about publication routes depending on local mandates (as in Germany) or individual funder policies (as in the UK). Some countries, such as France, Finland and Norway, have yet to reach agreement on the optimal funding model.

Co-ordination of policy across different organisations and governmental levels also matters. Austria, the Netherlands and (to a lesser extent) the UK and Denmark have brought policymakers, funders and institutions together and established an agreed strategy and set of principles to reach mandated countrywide OA, and most have already travelled some distance towards achieving this. In Germany's highly federalised system this is much harder and consequently most policies are recommendations rather than firm mandates. At the other end of the scale, the highly-centralised French system is also supporting recommendations rather than mandates, due to the difficulties in achieving consensus among stakeholders about appropriate funding structures. Individual institutions in every country may also have an open access policy or mandate for the academics they employ.

The Netherlands has also considered the international fit of its open access policies, seeking to lead and co-ordinate with other countries. In a similar vein, the Nordic countries in this study are collaborating with Sweden and Iceland to develop complementary policies (for open access in general) that respond to their local and particular circumstances.

Open access practices

High-level policy translates into (and in some cases comes into conflict with) established 'on the ground' practices among funders, publishers, institutions and researchers: this, too, affects possibilities for open access monographs.

Funding availability affects how Gold open access in particular can be implemented. Research funders in the UK and the Netherlands both 'primed the pump' with ring-fenced funds to support OA publications for research they had funded: FWF in Austria went even further with a dedicated fund that can be accessed by any Austrian academic, regardless of whether their original research was funded by FWF. At the other end of the scale, Danish funders generally do not set aside separate funds for OA publishing and some funders specifically prohibit spending their grant money on OA publishing costs.

In countries where Gold OA is more common, universities or research organisations may establish publication funds for their researchers: these are mostly used for journal articles at present but in many cases the institution is open to paying for books as well. Norway, in particular,

had significant institutional funds that were capable of supporting OA monographs. Monograph publishing models in Austria, Germany and the Nordic countries already rely on subsidies, and existing funders could consider making open access a condition of such payments in future (FWF in Austria has already done this).

Infrastructures for open access vary across countries. Some have taken steps towards legislation that encourages open access – Germany, for example, has included provisions for OA within federal copyright legislation, while France has enacted a Law for a Digital Republic which strongly encourages OA. The Netherlands has negotiated national deals with publishers to cover OA for all Dutch academics. Some countries have also made financial investments in publishing infrastructure to support OA: the most significant example is perhaps OpenEdition⁷ in France, a digital platform and ‘freemium’ business model to support digital and OA publishing, but the OAPEN platform in the Netherlands and the Finnish model of statefunded presses are also important.

Publishers and institutions also play an important role in providing the infrastructure for OA. Across all countries, most universities have a well established network of institutional repositories for academics pursuing the self-archiving route. Some, notably in Germany, also support university presses which mandate OA (without expecting any financial return to the institution). Publishers with a large international presence – in the Netherlands, the UK and Germany in particular – offer different models for OA monograph publishing, providing academics with a traditional outlet for open access publication. At the other end of the scale certain Norwegian publishers – working in a relatively small, native-language market – have developed OA publishing models, based on the availability in Norway of funding for BPCs which can cover all costs and revenues from traditional academic monographs.

Finally, there are some important **disrupters** stimulating new conversations about open access for monographs. In the UK, new university and academic-led presses are experimenting, not just with new business models but with new publishing formats, and modes of marketing, sales and distribution. In Germany, Language Science Press, a born-OA publisher, also offers open review and a comments option post-publication for monographs. Institutions from most countries in the study are signed up to Knowledge Unlatched, using crowd-sourced library funding to pay publication costs of OA monographs. These initiatives shift the conversation about what is possible.

Monograph publishing

Established monograph publishing practices affect the way that open access monographs are seen and the practical steps that must be taken to achieve them.

Funding models vary: in countries like Austria, Finland, Denmark, Norway and, to an extent, Germany, where many monographs are funded via subsidies, open access business models can repurpose the funds already associated with an individual book in order to make it OA. In very commercial environments like the UK and the Netherlands, where publishing costs are recovered primarily via sales, business models may require a more significant change. Although publishers may still repurpose existing funds – the Knowledge Unlatched model, for example, uses crowdfunding from library budgets – the underlying model for recovering publishing costs will shift. Of course in most countries the business models are mixed – France is the most extreme example of this, with a sector starkly divided between commercial lists that crossover into trade markets and university presses heavily subsidised by their parent institutions. Finland faces similar issues. In such environments, a ‘one size fits all’ model is problematic.

Footnotes

⁷ [openedition.org](https://www.openedition.org)

Maturity and international reach is also important. The UK, the Netherlands and some parts of the German academic publishing infrastructure are focused on global audiences and any changes to their systems must be implemented across multiple territories. For regional publishers such as those in Denmark, Finland, Austria and Norway, there's less pressure to work within different political and funding systems. On the flip side, larger international publishers are digital-ready, have already begun to embrace diverse funding streams and have well established systems of peer review which are trusted by funders. Smaller, national, publishing ecosystems find it harder to develop the infrastructure for global distribution. Peer review is a particular challenge, and Austria and Finland in particular are seeking a quality assurance process that is robust but not damaging to existing publishing practices (though in other Nordic countries peer review is well established). Language is also a challenge for countries that don't have a strong tradition of English language publishing, especially where

academics are keen to continue publishing in their native tongue (an important debate in the Nordic countries) or where the native-tongue market remains relatively strong (eg. in Germany and France).

The role of **monographs in scholarly cultures** is also important. Aside from academic attitudes to open access (something that was not in scope for this study), in some countries monograph publishing is tied to future funding. In the UK, institutions are judged periodically on their scholarly output, with a widely held perception that some publishers are considered more 'prestigious' than others within this exercise. In other countries, such as Finland, Norway, Denmark and (to a lesser extent) Austria, funders maintain national lists of 'authorised' research publication channels. Norwegian academics are also concerned that lower revenues from book sales and translation rights will lead to a decrease in funds (drawn from these sources) that are ploughed back into research.

Austria

For more on Austria, see [section 6.1](#) of the full report.

OA status	Working towards full OA by 2025
Gold or Green?	Gold preferred
Monographs included?	Yes
Monograph publishing industry	National, small

OA monographs have been **funded by FWF since 2009**, now mandated by them on funded projects, plus a competitive fund for researchers who want to publish OA monographs based on research funded from other sources. Austria's native subsidy-based monograph publishing model means transition to **OA is not a major change to business models**, and most Austrian publishers offer an open access scheme. **Creating a professional publishing industry** that can secure international visibility for monographs is the major challenge to open access monographs in Austria, as policy is already supportive of the transition.

Germany

For more on Germany, see [section 6.2](#) of the full report.

OA status	Depends on federal and state policies, hence varied
Gold or Green?	Both supported
Monographs included?	In discussions, not policies for most part
Monograph publishing industry	Several large international publishers, large long tail of smaller specialist publishers, university presses

For open access monographs, **developments led by university-funded presses**, some of which mandate OA. Nascent OA offerings from commercial publishers. Monographs not included in OA policies or budgets of most funders (DFG an exception), but **market pressures mean OA seems increasingly likely** as a viable business model. **Smaller publishers need to develop e-publishing infrastructure** to support digital OA output.

The Netherlands

For more on the Netherlands, see [section 6.3](#) of the full report.

OA status	Working towards full OA by 2020
Gold or Green?	Gold preferred
Monographs included?	Yes
Monograph publishing industry	Very concentrated: small number of large international publishers

NWO and Dutch universities have been exploring OA for monographs since 2008 and **publication funds have been available** from NWO and, recently, a small number of institutions. **Most academic book publishers offer OA**, and given that they are well established with international reach this should be an attractive option. But **author uptake does not seem high** and as yet it is unclear why this should be, given the Netherlands' well-developed and co-ordinated plan for moving towards OA.

France

For more on France, see [section 6.4](#) of the full report.

OA status	Strongly encouraged (and enabled by law) but not mandated
Gold or Green?	Not currently decided
Monographs included?	Not at the time of writing, but under discussion
Monograph publishing industry	French language: sharp divide between university and commercial presses

The divide between output of university presses (academic) and commercial publishers (wider 'trade' type audience in addition) makes **policy for OA monographs difficult**, with concerns that OA may lead to stricter boundaries between the two types. OpenEdition provides strong infrastructure, supported by national policies, but **appropriate funding models are a challenge**, due to the two very different business models operated by the two types of press: French policy currently focuses on the practicalities of resolving this problem during a transition period.

United Kingdom

For more on the United Kingdom, see [section 6.5](#) of the full report.

OA status	Mandated for publicly-funded research
Gold or Green?	Varies by funder
Monographs included?	Not currently but seems likely in future
Monograph publishing industry	Large, sales and authors sourced globally

Most commercial publishers have an OA offering and **new market entrants drive innovation** in OA as well as publication formats. Seems likely that monographs will be included in future mandates: the **challenge is business models and scalability** given that most UK publishers are not subsidised by institutions or publication fees. Long-term, a wide range of options/models most likely.

Denmark

For more on Denmark, see [section 6.7](#) of the full report.

OA status	Mandated for publicly funded research
Gold or Green?	Green
Monographs included?	No
Monograph publishing industry	Danish and other (especially English) language, small, non-commercial university presses

OA monographs are **not on the agenda at present**. Not included in mandates, little funding available, little demand from authors and hardly any experimentation by publishers.

Finland

For more on Finland, see [section 6.8](#) of the full report.

OA status	Mandated for publicly funded research
Gold or Green?	Both permitted
Monographs included?	Not currently
Monograph publishing industry	Small Finnish language, mostly learned society publishers and small library based university presses.

Publishers, funders and research organisations are **ready to experiment** and several small-scale trials are underway where **funds are available** and work agreed to be appropriate (English-language titles in particular). Barriers do remain, notably **author education and international visibility** for small Finnish publishers: platforms are important.

Norway

For more on Norway, see [section 6.9](#) of the full report.

OA status	Principles agreed, no mandate
Gold or Green?	Gold more common
Monographs included?	No
Monograph publishing industry	Integration between trade and monograph: small, Norwegian language

A **generally positive approach**. Some commercial publishers have OA options which are being used for highly-academic titles. OA for monographs is **excluded from national and institutional policies** because publication funds, though available from institutions and others, are not universal and researchers should not be punished for an inability to access funds.

New approaches to making monographs OA

Across all countries included within the studies (and some not included within this research), organisations were working in new ways, alone or in collaboration, to explore how best to support open access for monographs. These initiatives all provide opportunities to learn about how best to support OA monographs in different circumstances, and can be organised around 14 key themes.

	Publishers	Institutions	Libraries	Funders	Academics	Policymakers
Library-university press collaboration: from providing a basic publishing platform through to a full-service publisher		■	■			
New university press – traditional press collaboration: universities manage some aspects of publishing while outsourcing other elements to traditional publishers	■		■			
Including monographs in OA policies/mandates				■		■
Allowing BPCs to be paid from general OA publication funds: giving space for experimentation by authors, publishers and funders		■		■		
Co-ordinated approach to OA monographs: several funders working together to create joined-up policies and eventually mandates		■		■		■
Supporting investigation and experimentation: through pilot projects and research				■		■
Collaborative funding: aggregating funds from different institutions and individuals to crowd-fund OA monographs	■		■		■	
Public funding of an OA platform: government support of a platform and business model that facilitates OA monograph publishing				■		■
Supporting infrastructure development to set up OA book publishers: establishing new presses and sharing the learning that arises from this		■	■	■		
Building a disciplinary academic community around a new publishing venture: discipline-specific monograph ventures developed with academic support to secure credibility	■		■		■	
Examples of clear governance and structure around new presses: involving range of groups in new university presses to build credibility/engagement		■	■		■	
Collaboration on developing standards in and sharing of services for infrastructure: publishers in different territories have shared access to/understanding of infrastructure	■		■	■		■
Joint label to support quality assurance and dissemination: building scholarly trust in the outputs of OA monograph labels	■		■	■		
OA fund for aspects/types of monographs: providing flexibility that allows authors to cover all relevant costs associated with their OA monograph				■		■

Information gaps and future research direction

The report concludes with recommendations for different groups of stakeholders⁸. It also highlights areas where further information is still required and explores some of these in more detail via appendices.

Key areas where more information is needed, in order to establish the status quo and track future development of OA monographs, are⁹:

- ▶ Monograph output in numbers, geographically and by type
- ▶ OA monograph output (not all are currently available through the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)¹⁰)
- ▶ Compliance with OA requirements (funders, libraries and publishers), particularly a better understanding of how these requirements are communicated
- ▶ Quality assurance and service levels for books
- ▶ Self-archiving policies for books
- ▶ Publishing costs and how these relate to BPCs¹¹
- ▶ Understanding the impact of making a book OA¹²

Footnotes

⁸ For more on the recommendations to different groups, see [section 8.2](#) of the full report.

⁹ doabooks.org

¹⁰ For more on the information gaps, see [section 8.1](#) of the full report.

¹¹ For more information on BPCs and how these are calculated, see [section 10](#) of the full report.

¹² For more on understanding the impact of OA monograph publishing, see [section 11](#) of the full report.

Recommendations to OA stakeholders

In addition to research the report makes recommendations on actions that the various stakeholders might consider taking. These are summarised here.

Funders	Consider including monographs in their OA policies, and whether to move to mandating OA
	Partner with publishers and libraries to find novel solutions
	Make monographs part of open science with statements and policies acknowledging different formats and disciplines
	Be more transparent about what grant committees are looking for with regards to dissemination
	Streamline compliance and requirements in how BPCs are administered and monitored between funders
Policymakers	Be more aware of the importance of monographs
	Work with funders on cost effective ways to make monographs OA
	Consider mandating OA for books
Authors	To be brought more centrally into OA discussions
	Awareness of the benefits of OA to be raised through various professional bodies and misconceptions around OA books need to be tackled
University administrators	Should be encouraged to address issues around the reward system (including acknowledging value of OA, and its impact)
	Be more transparent about what tenure committees are looking for when reviewing applications
	Consider the Rentier solution: "it is only counted if it is in my (or other OA) repository"
	Look into how OA supports HSS
Publishers	Make it clear that monographs require different service levels for different purposes
	Be transparent about services and pricing
	Ensure information about different formats and pricing is presented clearly in one place
	Use a common set of metadata and list OA books in discovery systems (such as DOAB and elsewhere)
	Consider making backlist books with little commercial potential available OA retroactively
Libraries	Look at OA licensing and acquisitions in a coordinated manner
	Consider establishing collaborative programmes to reserve an increasing percentage of acquisitions budgets for OA books and infrastructure services
	Include OA monographs in their discovery systems (making use of DOAB)

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